
**SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE
DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVITY OF CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL
EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS**

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Abstract

In our republic, the production of the concept "Development of preschool education of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2030" No. PQ-4312 dated May 8, 2019 was released. The concept consists of areas for the development of preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, means of production, sustainable areas, areas of secondary and additional preschool education.

Key words

modern education, broadmindedness, democracy, leadership, free man, regulation, modern development, professional development.

When implementing this weapon, it is aimed to provide measures for the protection of the mental, intellectual, physical, spiritual profession of the younger generation in preschool educational organizations. It is inevitable that the state teacher has become the main executor of the social order set by society for the upbringing of the younger generation. In the modern world, the development of technologies and information processes, preschool education, the upbringing of a perfect person, providing him with modern education is the first problem that needs to be solved. It is the quality of education, determined by readiness for school, that becomes important and necessary in the reform of preschool education. In this regard, it is important to increase leadership abilities in providing education in preschool educational organizations with the introduction of modern lighting, management, innovation and information technologies in the process of providing education. In the implementation of this event, a preschool educational

organization requires high professional human tasks from each of the leaders. "First of all, he must have patriotism, love and honor his Motherland with all his heart, spare himself for his country and be ready to sacrifice his life if necessary. A master of his craft, a true expert in this work, is waiting for this or that example for others. He wants to be strong, noble, avoid dirty work, inquisitive, enterprising, organized, demanding and resolute." democratic state. production of necessity with skills. At the same time, one of the main requirements of the reform of preschool education is the education of specialists with great spiritual qualities that embody human abilities, working as mature personnel. This requirement of the time requires that students of preschool education be brought up morally and intellectually mature, perfect people. One of the most physical problems facing the leaders and teachers of the MTT is the problem observance of the spirituality of a free person. In other words, free, every citizen who recognizes his rights, understands his strengths and position, independently relates to the environment and events, and at the same time balances his private interests with the interests of the country and the protected people, it is necessary to educate literate people. At the same time, the upbringing of a comprehensively developed personality, first of all, requires great skill and responsibility from teachers. There is no ready-made pattern or template for the art of mentoring and nurturing. Mastering this art requires great strength, creativity and many years of experience. One of the foundations of the reform of preschool education in Uzbekistan is the research of a number of scientists on the issues of "personal interests and stability of education" in the education of a perfect personality. This is R.H. Jurayev, Zh.G'. Yuldoshev, S. Turgunov, R. Safarova, M. Yuldoshev, Sh.A. Abdullaeva, Yu.M. Asadov. As a result of the implementation of large-scale work on the fundamental reform of preschool education in Uzbekistan, scientific and pedagogical transformations of preschool education into a modern basic structure, into a modern educational and program base, into a material and technical base have been carried out, function effectively as educational institutions. Pedagogical and psychological foundations of the system of preschool education, state and non-state preschool educational institutions and pedagogical conditions for the organization of alternative types of documents, legal and regulatory framework for organizing the production of preschool educational institutions, the basics of world production, studying the technology of application to the educational process and the implementation of activities on this basis, work to put it into practice is gaining momentum. The issues of educating the younger generation in school education are among the important everyday professional

issues. At the same time, it is necessary to conduct, in harmony with the means of correction, regulation, supervision and control, in harmony with the means of correction, control and control, the tasks of intellectual maturity, morally healthy development of the individual are recognized. the publication of books and the scientific and spiritual revival of the teacher, the strengthening of the political and civil position. MTT requires extensive pedagogical knowledge, thorough practical training, high pedagogical skills, competence and creativity. Helping personal qualities are factors that provide a humanitarian factor in the process of preschool education: exactingness, truthfulness, honesty, kindness, politeness. Three qualities should determine the importance of a teacher for students. After all, personal qualities affect the ability to teach and educate.

Honorary President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev in his book "We will build our great future together with our brave and noble people": "Our task is to prepare the future generation, devoted to its people, capable of the production process, and competent in all aspects, they allow the idea that "to educate as a person." In fact, in the development of socio-economic relations of the century, the intellect and spirituality of a person manifest themselves as a developing factor and tool. Therefore, humanism appeared as the main test for building a legal, democratic state, a free civil society based on a market economy. The quality of education in the system of preschool education is a description of the professional development of the educator and development, as well as the recognition that it is determined by the development and labor activity of the development of professional activity in line with economic development in modern development. The quality of the educational process of a preschool educational institution, but not the educational process, its implementation, educational, program content, is associated with the acquired knowledge, skills and curricula of children, independently acquired knowledge. determined by the quality of education. The importance of the development of children, always progressing, intellectually and spiritually mature, physically and spiritually fresh in preschool education, the development of our country.

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